

Effect of Nutraceutical on Level of Antioxidant Vitamins in Lead (Pb) Intoxicated Rats

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Abstract

Environmental and occupational exposure to lead poses significant health risks due to its toxic nature, majorly attributed to its ability to incite oxidative stress. An antioxidant rich nutraceutical was administered to rats post lead-intoxication and during lead intoxication, targeted at increasing the level of antioxidant vitamins (A, C, and E) to complement and curb the lead-induced oxidative stress. Seven groups were formed and treated differently as positive control, negative control, normal control and four test groups. Curative and protective effects of the nutraceutical on the antioxidant vitamins level were evaluated by treating the two test groups with the nutraceutical during lead intoxication for the former and treating two other test groups with the nutraceutical post lead-intoxication for the latter at concentrations of 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg. The concentrations of vitamins A, C, and E were found to show a significant increase ($p < 0.05$). The effects were more remarkable in the protective experiment than in the curative experiment. Lead concentration also significantly decreased in all the treated groups for both protective and curative experiments. These findings indicate possible effectiveness of nutraceutical supplement in management and alleviation of lead toxicity.

Keywords: Antioxidants, Lead, Nutraceutical, Oxidative stress, Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS)

1.0 Introduction

Lead (Pb) is a toxic heavy metal with widespread distribution and persistence in the environment. Several health complications may arise from environmental and occupational exposure to lead [1]. Lead has no known physiological function and there is no acceptable threshold for lead exposure [1]. Exposure to lead in humans results in oxidative stress due to production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which is a key mechanism underpinning lead toxicity [2]. The production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydroperoxides (HO_2), singlet oxygen, and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), together with direct depletion of antioxidant reserves are the two distinct but connected mechanisms that cause oxidative stress [1,3]. When the generation of ROS rises in any biological system, antioxidant reserves are reduced [4].

Administering antioxidants could prevent and treat the harmful effects of lead resulting from production of free radicals in the body. Antioxidants can neutralize free radicals and stop their chain reaction by compensating their unpaired electrons and removing free radical intermediates, thereby becoming oxidized themselves in the process [5]. Plants and animals have a complex system comprising multiple types of antioxidants, such as vitamin C and vitamin E, as well as enzymes, such as catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and various peroxidases [6]. Some antioxidants such as vitamins are micronutrients which cannot be manufactured by the body itself and must be supplemented in the diet [7]. Studies have demonstrated the positive health impact and prevention of chronic diseases in consumption of antioxidant rich diet in the long run [8,9].

The high antioxidant properties of plant derived nutraceuticals make them strongly reliable in management of oxidative stress and lead toxicity [10]. Nutraceuticals are substances that are regarded as food or components of food which have health or medical benefits, such as prevention and treatment of diseases [11]. They are dietary supplements made of plant-based substances such as phytochemicals or bioflavonoids, as well as non-nutritive food ingredients like vitamins, minerals, and amino acids. A food that is naturally high in nutrients, such as spirulina, garlic, soy, or a particular part of a food, such as omega-3 oil from salmon, can be considered a nutraceutical [12].

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Chemicals

All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade. Lead acetate $[(C_2H_3O_2)Pb \cdot 3H_2O]$ was obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Germany) through local suppliers. Centrum obtained from Raudah Pharmaceutical company, Sokoto, Nigeria, was used as the standard vitamin supplement.

2.2 Nutraceutical Preparation

Antioxidant nutraceutical was prepared as described by Saidu et al. [13] with slight modifications. The nutraceutical was prepared locally by blending the following ingredients; 10g of tomatoes, 25g of onions, 25g of garlic, 10g of ginger, and 25g of smoothly blended dried water melon (*Citrullus lanatus*) seed sat $40^\circ C$. Ten (10)g of palm oil was then added and mixed thoroughly followed by 20g of lemon juice. The mixture was spread on a clean flat surface and allowed to dry at room temperature.

2.3 Experimental Animals

Thirty-five (35) albino rats of both sexes ranging from 200g to 280g in weight were obtained from Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. The animals were housed in polypropylene cages embedded with saw dust and acclimatized for 7 days prior to the experiment. The experimental animals were fed on standard rodent pellet and supplied with water *ad libitum*. All ethical guidelines and protocols for handling experimental animals by the Ethical Committee of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, were adhered to.

2.4 Experimental Design

The study involved two experiments aimed at determining the protective and curative effects of the nutraceutical supplement on levels of antioxidant vitamins A, C and E. The rats were randomly divided into 7 groups consisting of 5 rats each. All administrations were done orally.

Group 1 served as the normal control group and was given normal diet.

Group 2 only received 20mg/kg of lead acetate in their diet, serving as the negative control.

Group 3 received 10% (g/ml) of centrum, alongside 20mg/kg of lead acetate in their diet throughout the experiment, serving as the positive control.

Group 4 received 250mg/kg of nutraceutical alongside 20mg/kg of lead acetate in their diet throughout the experiment.

Group 5 received 500mg/kg of nutraceutical alongside 20mg/kg of lead acetate in their diet throughout the experiment.

Groups 1-5 were used for the protective effect experiment, while for the curative effects, groups 1-3 were maintained as the control groups in addition to the following groups.

Group 6 received 20mg/kg of lead acetate exclusively for the initial 14 days and then 250mg/kg of nutraceutical exclusively for the subsequent 14 days.

Group 7 received 20mg/kg of lead acetate exclusively for the initial 14 days and then 500mg/kg of nutraceutical for the subsequent 14 days.

The experiment was conducted for 28 days and animals were sacrificed on the 29th day.

2.5 Biochemical Analysis of Vitamins

Blood sample was collected from each rat by cardiac puncture at the end of the experiment then stored in red blood tube containers and subsequently centrifuged at 400rpm for 15 minutes.

Vitamin A was determined based on the addition of ethanol to break up the complex, permitting partitioning of vitamin A into heptanes. The nearly colorless retain is measured spectrophotometrically at 450nm[14].

Vitamin C was determined based on the formation of a green colored complex on reaction with phototung state (PR) which is measured spectrophotometrically at 700nm[15].

Vitamin E was determined based on the reduction of ferric ions to ferrous, which forms a red colored complex with α , α' -dipyridyl and absorbance measured at 539nm[16].

2.6 Determination of Lead (Pb) Concentration

Blood samples were analyzed for lead (Pb) concentration using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (Shimadzu-UK, "AAS3600") at the Energy Research Centre, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD and subjected to a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Statistical analysis was done using Instat3 statistical package. All results with values of $P < 0.05$ were considered significant.

3.0 Results

The nutraceutical was supplemented together with lead acetate in order to assess its protective effect on the levels of antioxidant vitamins A, C, E, and lead as shown in Table 3.1. The levels of vitamins A, C and E in the treated group were significantly improved by the nutraceutical in a dose-dependent manner compared to the untreated group ($P < 0.05$). The group treated with 500mg/kg of nutraceutical had vitamins C and E levels significantly higher than the centrum treated group ($P < 0.05$). There was also an accompanied decrease in the level of lead in treated groups against the untreated group.

Table 3.1. Protective effect of nutraceutical on vitamins A,C,E and lead

Group	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
Lead ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$)	ND	103.9 \pm 9.1	68.4 \pm 12.6	82.7 \pm 2.6	77.5 \pm 7.9
Vitamin A ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$)	72.91 \pm 9.36 ^a	49.21 \pm 6.65 ^b	82.21 \pm 2.22 ^a	81.67 \pm 17.64 ^a	102.63 \pm 27.63 ^a
Vitamin C (mg/dl)	2.29 \pm 0.46 ^{ab}	1.6 \pm 0.07 ^b	2.37 \pm 0.35 ^{ab}	2.52 \pm 0.35 ^{ab}	2.9 \pm 0.19 ^a
Vitamin E (mg/dl)	1.75 \pm 0.14 ^b	1.81 \pm 0.43 ^b	1.78 \pm 0.13 ^b	2.25 \pm 0.16 ^{ab}	2.66 \pm 0.27 ^a

Data are presented as Mean \pm SD, ^{a,b} Values with different superscripts are significantly different at $P < 0.05$

ND – Not detectable; Group 1- normal control group; Group 2-lead acetate untreated; Group 3-lead acetate treated with centrum; Group 4-lead acetate along with 250mg/kg of nutraceutical; Group 5-lead acetate along with 500mg/kg of nutraceutical

To further assess the curative effect of the nutraceutical on vitamins A, C, and E, the rats were supplemented with nutraceutical exclusively for 2 weeks after initial exposure to lead acetate exclusively for 2 weeks (Table 3.2). Vitamins A and E significantly increased in the treated group compared to the untreated group ($P < 0.05$). While

the level of vitamin E was significantly higher in nutraceutical treated groups than the group treated with centrum, reverse was the case for vitamin A ($P < 0.05$). Vitamin C was only slightly increased in the treated groups with no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Similarly, an accompanied decrease in the level of lead was observed.

Table 3.2. Curative effect of nutraceutical on vitamins A,C, E, and lead

Group	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 6	Group 7
Lead ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$)	ND	103.9 \pm 9.1	68.4 \pm 12.6	86.6 \pm 19.7	57.8 \pm 23.6
Vitamin A ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$)	72.91 \pm 9.36 ^a	49.21 \pm 6.65 ^c	82.21 \pm 2.22 ^a	55.59 \pm 3.6 ^b	67.98 \pm 9.66 ^b
Vitamin C (mg/dl)	2.29 \pm 0.46	1.6 \pm 0.07	2.37 \pm 0.35	1.61 \pm 0.1	1.79 \pm 0.11
Vitamin E (mg/dl)	1.75 \pm 0.14 ^b	1.81 \pm 0.43 ^{ab}	1.78 \pm 0.13 ^b	2.24 \pm 0.15 ^{ab}	2.29 \pm 0.13 ^a

Data are presented as Mean \pm SD, ^{a,b}Values with different superscripts are significantly different at $P < 0.05$

ND – Not detectable; Group 1- normal control group; Group 2-lead acetate untreated; Group 3-lead acetate treated with centrum; Group 4-lead acetate exclusively in the first 2 weeks and 250mg/kg of nutraceutical exclusively in the subsequent 2 weeks; Group 5-lead acetate exclusively in the first 2 weeks and 500mg/kg of nutraceutical exclusively in the subsequent 2 weeks.

4.0 Discussion

High amounts of lead were detected in the blood samples indicating that lead exposure has been well established. Furthermore, treatment with both centrum and nutraceutical significantly reduced blood levels of lead. Although centrum showed higher efficacy, the nutraceutical was also significantly effective in reducing the levels of lead in blood. This indicates possible chelation property of some compounds contained in the nutraceutical, of which vitamin C is included.

The antioxidant activity of vitamin A remains unconfirmed despite claims of its possible roles as a prooxidant [17]. However, lead exposure remarkably affected the amount of vitamin A in blood. These effects were completely reversed by the nutraceutical supplement, with more pronounced amelioration in the protective group which may be due to a longer treatment duration. Some forms of vitamin A such as β -carotene mediate prevention of lipid peroxidation, and reduces the incidence of many diseases including cancer, atherosclerosis, age-related macular degeneration, and multiple sclerosis [18].

Vitamin C is a well-known free radical scavenger that is highly effective in heavy metal chelation and amelioration of lead toxicity [19,20,21]. Its level was significantly decreased upon exposure to lead. The nutraceutical sufficiently prevents decline in vitamin C more effectively than centrum when supplemented during lead-exposure. The curative effect was less pronounced

possibly because the treatment duration was shorter and lead toxicity have been more established.

The powerful antioxidant activity of vitamin E could be remarkably maintained by the nutraceutical supplement [22]. Although its level was not affected when compared to the normal group, the nutraceutical supplement still increased the amount of vitamin E in the blood. Studies have shown natural antioxidants to be more effective when combined, particularly vitamins C and E [23]. The remarkable improvement of all three vitamins could provide desired synergistic effect.

5.0 Conclusion

The body require adequate supply of antioxidants to counter the increased production of reactive oxygen species and free radicals in lead toxicity [24]. The nutraceutical supplement was compounded from different fruits and vegetables that can be easily obtained and known to contain antioxidant compounds. The nutraceutical in this study reliably increased the level of vitamins A, C, and E thereby increasing the antioxidant status of the rats. There was a remarkable decrease in the level of lead which suggests chelation potential of the nutraceutical. The nutraceutical could provide a reliable source of antioxidants to aid in management of lead toxicity and oxidative stress.

6.0 Recommendations

The nutraceutical supplement effectively improved the level of antioxidant vitamins A, C, and E with an accompanied decrease in lead concentration. Further analysis to determine its effectiveness on oxidative stress parameters as well as other active compounds will be necessary to understand its mechanism of action. Toxicological study is also necessary to determine safe levels of the nutraceuticals and identify if there are adverse effects.

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8.0 Conflicts of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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